

PREDICTION OF DAMAGE WIDTH IN LASER DRILLING OF PRINTED WIRING BOARD USING FEM

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SUMMARY: The temperatures are measured at the various positions from the drilled hole wall during laser drilling of PWB using the thermocouples. It is found that these temperatures are dependent on the individual values of materials in the composites. Moreover, we pay attention to the properties of the glass fiber as an analytical model of FEM in order to predict the carbonized damage widths after laser drilling in PWB. The measured temperature is substituted for the boundary condition at the inside diameter of drilled hole, and the other boundaries are insulated against the heat transfer. As results, the damage widths defined as carbonizing on an experiment are good agreement with calculated ones.

KEYWORDS: GFRP, printed wiring board, CO₂ laser, damage, drilling, laser drilling, FEM

INTRODUCTION

The printed wiring board (PWB) has been smaller, because the demand for reducing the size of the electric devices has become to increase. Therefore, laser drilling has been considered as an effective method to machine the smaller through holes (less than diameter 0.3 mm) in PWB. In the case of PWB made of composite materials, it is necessary to improve the heat affect zone (carbonized zone) at the hole wall for application of laser drilling. However, there has been few studies[1,2,3] which dealt with the hole quality of laser drilling of GFRP. So, this paper describes the damage due to the heat influence in laser drilling in PWB, which is made of GFRP (epoxy / glass woven cloth, thickness 1.6 mm), using a CO₂ source.

First, the temperatures are measured at the various positions from the drilled hole wall using the thermocouples in order to research the distributions of temperatures around the hole during laser drilling of PWB. On the other hand, the heat affected damages around the hole are observed using the optical microscope. The relations between the damages and the temperatures of the hole wall are investigated from these results.

Second, the heat transfer is analyzed to predict the damage width at drilled hole wall after laser drilling using FEM. Specially, we pay attention to the properties of the glass fiber as an analytical model. The measured temperature is substituted for the boundary condition at the

inside diameter of the drilled hole, and the other boundaries are insulated against the heat transfer. The calculations are carried out to compare the experimental results under various laser irradiation times.

Finally, the carbonized damage widths on the calculated model are defined as the distances from the inside diameter at the minimum temperature in the area where the epoxy resin is carbonized on experiments. It is shown that the model with these boundary conditions based on this experiment is effective on predicting the carbonized damage widths after laser drilling in PWB.

EXPERIMENTAL EQUIPMENT AND MATERIALS

The maximum attainable power of a CO₂ laser is 250 W. The drilling is performed on the conditions of 150W, 75 W and 35 W in this study. The spot diameter is 0.3 mm on the just focus, and the lens is 5 inches. N₂ is used as the assisting gas in laser drilling.

GFRP is the type of glass (39 in mass) /epoxy-resin, plain woven cloth and thickness 1.6 mm. The workpiece is the copper clad laminate for PWB. The properties of the glass and the epoxy resin are shown in Table 1.

Fig.1 shows the diagram of measuring the temperatures during laser drilling. The thermocouples (0.1 mm) are inserted between GFRPs of thickness 0.8mm. In other words, measuring points are 0.8 mm from the surface. The signals from the sensors are recorded by the memory recorder with the signals of the shutter of a laser beam. The workpiece is mounted on the X-Y table. The distances from the hole wall are determined by observing the workpieces using the microscope after laser drilling.

Table 1: Properties of GFRP

Glass	E-glass		Composition (wt%)			
	Diameter	10 μ m	SiO ₂	54	MgO	5
Tensile strength	3.43 GPa	Al ₂ O ₃	14	B ₂ O	8	
Young's modulus	73 GPa	CaO	18			
Epoxy	Bending modulus of elasticity		19 GPa			
	Bending strength		130 MPa			

Fig.1: Experimental equipment

Fig.2: Temperature and time (Laser output power 150W)

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Measured Results of Temperature in Laser Drilling

Fig.2 shows the relations between time and the temperatures at various distances from hole wall during laser drilling. The laser irradiation time is in the case of 0.5 s. The inclination of increasing the temperature is higher at the measuring point near the drilled hole wall during the laser irradiation period. The maximum temperatures are indicated earlier at this measuring point, too. It is found from these results that the heat transfer from the hole wall causes an increase of the temperature around the hole. At the distance of 0.2 mm from the hole wall, the maximum

Fig.3: Maximum temperature and distance from hole wall (In the case of the epoxy resin, Laser output power 150 W)

Fig.4: Maximum temperature and distance from hole wall (In the case of GFRP, Laser output power 150 W)

temperature indicates more than 1000 (1273 K). It is shown near the hole wall that the temperature is very high during laser drilling of GFRP.

Maximum Temperature in Laser Drilling

Fig.3 shows the relations between the maximum temperatures and the distances from the hole wall in laser drilling of the epoxy resin (in the case of the irradiation time 0.1s). Fig.4 shows the relations between the maximum temperatures and the distances from the hole wall in laser

drilling of GFRP (in the case of the irradiation time 0.5s). In the case of laser drilling of the epoxy resin , the thermal decomposition (pyrolysis) and the complete combustion of the epoxy resin are carried out in a moment and the heat affected damage hardly appears at the drilled hole wall [3]. From Fig.3, it is found that the maximum temperatures are low values nearest the hole wall, and the heat input is small from the hole wall in laser drilling of the epoxy resin. On the other hand, it is found from fig.4 that the temperatures are very high values near the hole wall, and the heat input is very large from the hole wall in laser drilling of GFRP. Moreover, the maximum temperature estimated from fig.4 nearest the drilled hole is approximately from 2500 to 3000 (from 2773 K to 2273 K) in drilling.

Damage after Laser Drilling

Fig.5(a) shows the microscope photograph of the hole entrance of GFRP after laser drilling in the case of the irradiation time 0.5s, and Fig.5(b) shows the glass cloth in drilled GFRP whose resin is vaporized at 600. This damage is hardly dependent on the fiber direction, because we can see the circle damage zone in Fig.5. By comparison of Fig.5(a) with Fig.5(b), we can see that the black substance in the heat affected damage is separated into the carbon (vaporization at 600) and others (no vaporization). The width of the former from hole wall is 0.8 mm and that of the latter is 0.3mm. Furthermore, by comparison of these widths with the maximum temperatures in Fig.4, it is found that the former area is from 500 to 1300 (from 773 K to 1573 K), and the latter area is more than 1300 (1573 K).

Details of the heat affected zones follow: the epoxy resin (low resolution point) is decomposed by the thermal conduction of the glass fibers at 500 (773 K), and then the pyrolytic carbon deposits on the glass fibers. Thus, the surface of the glass fibers turns to black. Additionally, the temperature of the glass fibers near the hole wall rises to more than melting point of the glass. At more than 1200 (1473 K) SiO_2 (glass fiber) is reduced to SiC by the carbon, and at more than 1500 (1773 K) the carbon varies to the graphite. As results, the carbon on the glass fibers varies to the graphite and SiC . This is the black zone in Fig.5(b). In other words, it is clear that these temperatures during drilling are dependent on the individual values of the material in the composites.

PREDICTION OF DAMAGE WIDTH

The heat affected zone is an important factor to consider the laser drilling as the new smaller diameter drilling method for the through hole. Therefore, it is necessary to estimate the distributions of the temperatures around the hole wall in various drilling conditions. So, the heat transfer analysis is carried out by FEM using boundary conditions based on above experiments.

Analytical Model

From experimental results, it is found that the heat transfer are more affected by the glass fibers than the epoxy resin in laser drilling of GFRP. So, we attract attention to the maximum temperatures at the hole wall during laser drilling, and to the properties of E glass as the material properties. In this model, the anisotropy of material properties is taken into no account, because the damage can be seen as the circle damage zone, and is hardly dependent on the fiber direction from Fig.5. The temperatures at the drilled hole wall is the sublimation temperature of SiC (2800) (3073 K) from Fig.4 . Other boundaries are insulated against the heat transfer, because the laser irradiation time is very short in laser drilling of PWB. The

specific gravity is 2.54, the thermal conduction rate is 1.04 W/mK, and the specific heat is 800 J/kgK. The radius of the drilled hole wall at the model is the radius of the spot diameter of a laser beam. The heat transfer analysis of the non-steady heat conduction is carried out by FEM on these boundary conditions.

*Fig.5: Microscope photograph of hole entrance
(Laser output power 150 W, Irradiation time 0.5 s)*

Distributions of Temperatures

Fig. 6 shows the calculated results of the relations between the distances from the hole wall and the temperatures after 0.1s , 0.5s and 1.0s. Comparing Fig.4 and a calculated result after 0.5s, it is found that a calculated result is in good agreement with the experimental one. From these results, this model is effective to estimate the distributions of the maximum temperatures in laser drilling of GFRP.

Prediction of Damage Width

The black zone (carbonizing zone) in Fig.5(a) is an important area where the epoxy resin is decomposed, because this is an uneven area along the thickness of GFRP and a change in quality by the heat affect. Accordingly, this width has the influence on the reliability of the through hole plating of PWB. So, the prediction of heat affect damage widths is carried out using the calculated temperatures by this method.

That is: the areas more than 500 (773 K) are defined as the black zone (carbonizing zone) at calculated results in laser drilling. Fig.7 shows the calculated result and the microscope photograph of a experimental result in the same scale (irradiation time 0.5s and calculated after 0.5s). Fig.8 shows the relations between the irradiation time and the damage widths in the case of various laser output powers. From these figures, it is found that the damage widths after drilling of GFRP under various irradiation time can be predicted using the threshold of this temperature in this model.

Fig.6: Calculated temperature and distance from hole wall

Fig.7: Comparison between experimental result and calculated one

Fig.8: Damage widths and irradiation times

CONCLUSION

1. From measuring the temperatures in GFRP during laser drilling, it is found that the heat transfer from the hole wall causes an increase of the temperature around the hole. The temperatures are low values nearest the hole wall, and the heat input is small from the hole wall in laser drilling of the epoxy resin. On the other hand, the temperatures are very high values near the hole wall, and the heat input is very large from the hole wall in laser drilling of GFRP. The drilled hole temperature is approximately from 2500 to 3000 (from 2773 K to 2273 K) during drilling of GFRP.
2. Details of the heat affected zones become clear from the view point of the temperatures in laser drilling of GFRP: the epoxy resin (low resolution point) is decomposed by the thermal conduction of the glass fibers at 500 (723 K), and then the pyrolytic carbon deposits on the glass fibers. So, the surface of the glass fibers turns to black. Additionally, the temperature of the glass fibers near the hole wall rises to more than melting point of the glass. At more than 1200 (1473 K) SiO₂ (glass fiber) is reduced to SiC by the carbon, and at more than 1500 (1773 K) the carbon varies to the graphite.
3. The heat transfer is analyzed to predict the damage width (carbonizing zone) at the drilled hole wall using FEM. Specially, we attract attention to the maximum temperatures at the hole wall during laser drilling, and to the properties of E glass as the material properties. The temperature at the drilled hole wall is fixed at the sublimation temperature of SiC (2800) (3073 K) . Other boundaries are insulated against the heat transfer. As results, it is found that this model is effective to estimate the distributions of the maximum temperatures in laser drilling of GFRP. The damage widths after drilling of GFRP under various irradiation times can be predicted using the threshold of 500 (773 K) in this model.

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